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Research Article

**A CLINICO-PATHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF BENIGN
BREAST LUMPS**¹Muhammad Umar Farooq, ²Rafia Batool, ³Dr Muhammad Usama Khalid¹Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur²Rawalpindi Medical College, Rawalpindi³Avicenna Medical College, Lahore**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Breast disease is one of the most common diseases of women in any society. The purpose of this study was to discover the pattern of benign breast lumps in women.

Place and Duration: *In the Surgical Unit-II and Pathology department of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for one-year duration from April 2019 to April 2020.*

Methods: *Of the 400 women; 98 were diagnosed with a breast lump were included. We performed FNAC on every woman who developed a breast lump to obtain a correct histopathological diagnosis.*

Results and Conclusion: *Out of 98 patients, 52 women were diagnosed with benign breast disease, included in our study. Of these 52 women, 37 had fibroadenomas, 13 had fibroadenomas, and 2 had recurrent fibrous adenomas.*

Key words: *breast lump, benign, FNAC*

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INTRODUCTION:

Benign breast lumps are the most common lesions, accounting for over 90% of the presented breast-related cases. Fibrous adenoma is a common cause of benign breast lumps in premenopausal women. Breast fibrocystic disease is a histological term that refers to a large group of syndromes characterized by a lump or tumor. Fibrous adenomas are the most common cause of benign breast lumps. They usually appear as single, firm, rubbery and insensitive lumps. Further research has shown that there is a link between benign breast disease and breast cancer. The risk of cancer varies with the histological evaluation of benign breast disease. Therefore, all breast lumps are carefully examined to rule out malignancy. The aim of this study is to find out about the pattern of benign breast lumps in women admitted to our hospital of the third degree. The study is observational, non-interventional and prospective.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Surgical Unit-II and Pathology department of Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for one-year duration from April 2019 to April 2020. Of 98 female patients aged 15-45, 52 had benign breast disease. The management protocol included a clinical examination, followed by mammography in selected cases and FNAC in all patients. Of these 52 women with benign breast lumps with or without pain were included in our study, and women with malignant lesions were excluded. Notches were made as a specific procedure. A record of the histopathological results was kept. Other variables noted were age, birth, marital status, and family history of breast disease.

RESULTS:

Of 98 female patients aged 15-45, 52 had benign breast disease. The most common symptom was fibroadenoma in 37 patients [71%], followed by fibrocystic disease, 13 [25%] and 2 [4%] had recurrent fibrous adenoma, i.e. postoperative adenomas on the same breast or on the other side. Table 1 explains this further. Some common factors in the history of these patients are described in Table 2.

Table 1:

Type of Lumps	=n	%age
Fibro adenoma	37	71
Fibrocystic Disease	13	25
Recurrent Fibro adenoma	2	4

Table 2:

Common Factors	%age
Marital Status (Unmarried)	63
Poor Socio-economic Status	81

Of these 52 breast lumps, 35 were painless and only 17 were painful. Of these 17 painful nodules, 11 were fibrocystic and 6 were fibrous adenomas. Most of the lumps were in the right breast. 7 Patients with fibrocystic disease develop symptoms within 6 months, 3 patients develop symptoms within 4 to 5 months and 1 patient develop symptoms within 3 months. 4 patients with fibromatous adenoma developed symptoms within 2 months and 2 patients experienced symptoms within 1 month. In this study, the mean age of benign breast disease was 35 years, with a range of 15-45 years. Most of the lumps were in the right breast, i.e. 32.41 out of 52 women were unmarried.

Figure 1:

DISCUSSION:

In our society, benign breast diseases are much more common than malignant breast diseases. All of these conditions usually present as a breast lump, breast pain or nipple discharge etc. but due to a lack of knowledge and awareness, women ignore the lump. Fibrous adenoma is the most common benign breast tumor in our society and the patient wants to have it removed for fear of malignancy or for cosmetic reasons. In this study, the 52 patients who came to us with mild breast disease were between the ages of 15 and 45. 11 out of 52 patients were married, aged 30 to 45, gave birth to 5 to 8 children. The average age was 35. 41 of 52 patients were single, aged 15 to 22 years. Of these 52 breast lumps, 35 were painless and only 17 were painful. Interestingly, it has been noticed that the incidence of fibrocystic disease and fibrocystic adenoma of the breast is quite variable in each society. According to our research, 13 [25%] patients were patients with fibrocystic disease. This percentage is similar to the study by Chaudhry et al. From India, 25.5%. By contrast, this figure is lower than other studies by Jamal et al. From Saudi Arabia 36%, Thekwaba 29.2% from Nigeria, 42% from Nigeria according to Adesunkanmi. Out of 52 patients, 2 had recurrent fibroids, which is 3.85%, which is more than Onuigbo who mentioned 1.32% of recurrent fibroids. Some lumps were painful and tender, while others were painless. Out of 52 patients, 41 were unmarried. This shows that benign breast disease is more common in unmarried women. No specific nutritional pattern has been noted. Most of the patients in our study belonged to people with a lower socio-economic status (working class). Our findings support the existing evidence that in our society fibrous adenomas are the most common benign breast disease followed by fibrocystic disease. This may be related to certain environmental, regional, dietary or hormonal factors that require further investigation and evaluation.

CONCLUSION:

The results of this study showed that benign breast diseases in women in our society are fibrocystic adenomas followed by fibrocystic diseases. The actual factors responsible for this change require further research and study.

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